

**Research on the improvement of
inter-laminar shear strength of
CFRTP using MWCNT double
introducing method**

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Introduction – Engineering plastic (Thermoplastic)

| Introduction – Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymer

CFRTP

= Carbon fiber + Thermoplastic = Interface property

Advantages

Impact resistance

Recycle (reforming)

Unlimited shelf life

Ability to be welded

Short processing time

High chemical resistance

Disadvantages

High melting temperature

High viscosity

Cool down step

Low surface free energy

Impregnation with fibers

Interfacial bonding strength

Introduction – CFRTP interface property

- **Carbon fiber + PA 6 matrix**

- Mechanical properties of the FRP is determined by the interface
- Impossible to construct the composite
- Chemical (surface treatment) or mechanical (nano filler) method

Introduction – Surface treatment and Nano filler

• Surface treatment

@출처: Nischith Raphael, Surface modification and grafting of carbon fibers: A route to better interface, Progress in crystal growth and characterization of materials, 2018.11

- **Induce the functional group on the surface**
: -OH / -COOH / C-O
- Plasma, Gamma, Oxidation, chemical oxidation and element treatment

• Nano filler reinforcement

- CNT, graphene, silica, metal and etc.
- Simply mixing with matrix
- **Directly growing**
- **Synthesizing or CVD**

MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber

- CNT anchoring for load transfer
- Chemical + mechanical
- Mass production possible
: Applicable for large area
- Low price treatment

MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber fabrication process

MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber chemical bonding

Acid-treated MWCNT

Coupling agent coated CF

MWCNT anchored carbon fiber

MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber chemical bonding

- **Pristine carbon fiber**

- **2 wt.% MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber**

- **4 wt.% MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber**

Cross section

MWCNT-anchored CF RTP fabrication

- Materials**

- T700 carbon fiber reinforcement
- PA 6 powder (< 150 μm)
- MWCNT 20~30 nm diameter and 10~30 μm length

- Hot compression mold**

- Specimens**

Reference specimen

Reinforcement
Matrix

Pristine carbon fiber Pure PA6
powder

MWCNT-mixed CF RTP

Reinforcement
Matrix

Pristine carbon fiber MWCNT
mixed PA6 powder

MWCNT concentrations (wt.%) in the
PA6 Matrix

1, 3, 5 wt.%

MWCNT-anchored CF RTP

Reinforcement
Matrix

MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber
Pure PA6 powder

MWCNT concentrations (wt.%) in the
MWCNT dispersed water

1, 2, 3, 4 wt.%

Tensile test results

• MWCNT simply mixed with matrix

➤ Inter-laminar failure

• MWCNT-anchored CFRTTP

➤ Tensile failure or fiber pull-out

Inter-laminar shear strength

- MWCNT simply mixed with matrix**

- MWCNT-anchored CFRTTP**

Inter-laminar shear failure surface

- **Pristine carbon fiber**

- **1 wt.% MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber**

- **4 wt.% MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber**

Izod impact strength

- **MWCNT simply mixed with matrix**

- **MWCNT-anchored CFRTTP**

Izod impact strength

- **Pristine carbon fiber**

- **1 wt.% MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber**

- **3 wt.% MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber**

- **4 wt.% MWCNT-anchored carbon fiber**

Double introduced MWCNT & entanglements

- Micro bridging effect between MWCNTs entanglement

Double introduced MWCNT & entanglements

• Materials

- Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) powder (PEEK150UF10)
- Particle size $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$
- **Melting point $\sim 343^\circ\text{C}$**
- **Processing Temp. $\sim 400^\circ\text{C}$**

• Hot compression mold

• Specimens

MWCNT anchored on CF	MWCNT mixed with matrix			
	0	1 wt.%	2 wt.%	3 wt.%
0	<i>REF</i>			
1 wt.%	<i>F1</i>	<i>F1+M2</i>	<i>F1+M3</i>	
2 wt.%	<i>F2</i>	<i>F2+M1</i>	<i>F2+M3</i>	
3 wt.%	<i>F3</i>			

Double introduced MWCNT & entanglements

• MODE 1 Fracture toughness

• *REF* had a fracture toughness of **741.4 J/m²**. The fracture toughness of *F2* specimens (with 2 wt.% MWCNTs anchored on the CF) increased by 50% to **1130.4 J/m²**.

• Optimal concentration of the double MWCNTs reinforcing was *F2+M1*, and the fracture toughness further increased by 61.7% to **1202.2 J/m²**.

Double introduced MWCNT & entanglements

• Inter-laminar shear strength

• Optimal concentration for the ILSS of the double MWCNTs reinforcing was also *F2+M1*, and the ILSS increased by 63.4% to **98.2 MPa**.

• It was confirmed that the interfacial bonding strength was significantly improved compared to the specimen in which MWCNTs were only attached to the carbon fiber.

Fracture surface after the mode 1 test

- *REF*

➤ Clean surface

- *F2+M1*

➤ Uni-direction fracture due to bridge effect

- *F2*

➤ Visibility of MWCNTs within the fractured area

- *F2+M3*

➤ *F2+M3* - MWCNT aggregation

Conclusions

- **MWCNT-anchored carbon fibers** were developed to improve the impact resistance and ILSS of CFRTPs. The MWCNTs were chemically anchored on the CF through an **esterification reaction**.
- **Simply mixing MWCNTs with the thermoplastic matrix** increased the Izod impact resistance of the resulting CFRTP; however, it **decreased the corresponding ILSS** due to the increased resin viscosity.
- The **ILSS and the impact resistance** of the MWCNT-anchored CFRTP were **increased by 34% and 91%**, respectively, with optimum MWCNT-anchoring concentrations.
- By **double MWCNTs reinforcing** on CF (2 wt.%) and with thermoplastic matrix (1 wt.%), the ILSS of the **PEEK based CFRTP increased by 63.4% to 98.2 MPa**.
It is the results of the **strong entanglement between the doubly introduced MWCNTs** prevented crack propagation and maximized the fracture length.

Thank you

Q & A

